

Condensation of chromatin in human buccal epithelium cells after training sessions

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Abstract

In purpose to assess the effect of physical loadings on cytological characteristics of human cells, the heterochromatin granules quantity (HGQ) was assessed in cells of human buccal epithelium. HGQ was assessed among trained and untrained students during volleyball and tennis training sessions three times – before, in the process and after training session. HGQ increased during training sessions in volleyball and tennis. This parameter increased with time of performance of the training session. The assessment of HGQ in buccal epithelium cells is recommended as a cytological criterion of answer of organism of athletes to training sessions.

Keywords

sportive charges, volleyball, tennis, cell nucleus, heterochromatin, chromatin condensation

Introduction

The problem of the objective assessment of the functional state of human organism is important in many areas of science, for instance, in medicine: the assessment of the state of the human organism in the course of medical treatment; in occupational physiology for assessment of the influence of conditions of labor on human organism, and in sports medicine. There are many methods to assess the state of the human organism in sport medicine based on the study of physiological and biochemical characteristics [1]. Sport exercise in healthy people impacts on several areas, including maximal oxygen uptake, central hemodynamic function, autonomic nervous system function, peripheral vascular and muscular function, and submaximal exercise capacity. Many muscle properties change during fatigue including the action potential, extracellular and intracellular ions, and many intracellular metabolites [2]. One of the popular biochemical methods of estimation of intensity of muscular work is the determination of lactate concentration in blood. A link between lactate and muscular exercise was seen more than 200 years ago. The blood lactate concentration (BLC) is sensitive to changes in exercise intensity and duration [3]. But in some works no connections between exercise intensity and biochemical markers of muscle exercise are shown. The maximal lactate steady state (MLSS) and MLSS intensity are independent of performance but subjects with higher maximum performance have higher MLSS workloads [4]. There was observed no significant difference in BLC, creatinin kinase (CK), malondialdehyde (MDA), uric acid (UA), and total and differential leukocytes between groups of healthy

untrained men performing moderate intensity (MI) and high intensity (HI) sport exercise ($P > 0.05$) [5]. Besides, the biochemical methods of estimation of physical load intensity are connected with collection of samples of blood and therefore are traumatic. All this causes the necessity of development of new simple methods of analysis. Previously we have proposed a method for estimation of effects of training loads by degree of chromatin condensation in cells of buccal epithelium. Chromatin – the complex of DNA and proteins located in cell nucleus may be present in two forms – euchromatin and heterochromatin. The heterochromatin is a condensed, intensively stained, and low functionally active form of chromatin [6]. The degree of condensation of chromatin increased during cross-country and it decreased after a period of repose [7]. The simple method of counting number of granules of heterochromatin in the nucleus of buccal epithelium cell gives a lot of information about the state of cell subjected to different stresses [8].

The aim of the present study was to investigate the microscopic characteristic of chromatin - number of granules of heterochromatin in nuclei of buccal epithelium after gradual increase of physical load in the process of performance of sport exercises in groups of trained and untrained people.

Materials and Methods

Cells

The buccal cells were obtained from the surface of the donor's cheek by light scrapping with a blunt spatula; this operation is absolutely bloodless and painless. The informed donors-volunteers were students of V.N. Karazin Kharkiv National University. The study was performed in accordance with the European Convention on Human Rights and

Biomedicine (1997) and also of Declarations and Recommendations of the First, the Second and the Third National (Ukrainian) Congresses of Bioethics (Kiev, Ukraine, 2001, 2004, 2007) and Ukrainian legislation. All participants gave written informed consent prior to participation in the research.

Two groups of students: one of 7 untrained students and the other group of 7 students - Candidates for Master of Sports (volleyball) performed the training sessions (playing volleyball) within 120 min. Two other groups of tennis players: one of 7 untrained students and other group of 5 students - Candidates for Master of Sports (lawn-tennis) performed training session (playing tennis) within 60 min. The average age of donors was (21 ± 1.5) years. Samples of buccal epithelial cells were collected by scraping with a blunt sterile spatula from cheek mucosa and immediately stained by orcein. Cells were collected just before, during and after the performance of training session.

Cell staining

The number of heterochromatin granules was assessed in nuclei of human buccal epithelium cells. Cells were stained with 2% orcein solution in 45% acetic acid for 30 min, and then

examined at magnification 600x. The granules of heterochromatin can be clearly seen in the cell nucleus stained with orcein (Fig. 1), which allows to introduce a quantitative characteristic - heterochromatin granule quantity (HGQ). The cells of buccal epithelium look almost the same in all cases: untrained and trained students, before and after training sessions. The changes in cells are not qualitative changes but only quantitative changes – increases the number of granules of heterochromatin and this difference hardly may be visible in a small number of cells. The increase in HGQ is the same after training sessions in volleyball and in tennis, so we present, as an example of changes related to training session, the photographs of cells of untrained student (Donor A) before and after training session in tennis. The average number of heterochromatin granules in one nucleus was assessed and then calculated the average value of the HGQ in 30 nuclei [9]. Statistical analysis was done by Student's t-test. The level of statistical significance of differences between variants applied in this work is $p > 0,95$. The variants significantly different from control are marked with asterisks in Figs 2-3.

Figure 1 Cells of human buccal epithelium stained with orcein (cells of untrained student Donor-A before (a) and after training session (b) in tennis, 60 min.)

Results

The results of the experiment with cells of volleyball players are presented in Fig. 2.

Figure 2 HGQ in nuclei of buccal epithelium cells of volleyball players before, during and after training session: A) – untrained players, B) – qualified players

To assess the effect of physical activity on the HGQ in buccal cells we compared cells obtained before, during and after sportive exercise. As it can be seen from Fig. 2A, in the group of untrained students the HGQ ranges from 19,9 to 22,9; mean $21,49 \pm 0,17$. After 60 min of exercise HGQ is changed to levels of 22,7 – 24,0; mean $23,45 \pm 0,17$. The HGQ after 60 min of sportive session was significantly higher for each donor. Further training resulted in the increase of the HGQ to the level 24,3 - 26,6; mean $25,63 \pm 0,20$. In the group of trained students, results are presented in Fig. 2B, the changes in HGQ resembled those observed in the group of untrained students. Cells of the trained students in control had the same HGQ level 18,5 – 21,9 (mean $21,13 \pm 0,17$) but at the stage of training for 60 min, HGQ rose to the level 21,6 – 23,9 (mean $22,26 \pm 0,18$), that is less, than in group of untrained students. After 120 min of training HGQ rose to 24,6 – 27,2 (the mean $26,03 \pm 0,22$), that is

close to the HGQ level in the group of untrained students in the same situation.

Figure 3 HGQ in nuclei of buccal epithelium cells of tennis players before, during and after training session: A) – untrained players, B) – qualified players

HGQ changes in buccal epithelium cells during training session in tennis (Fig. 3) are in good agreement with the HGQ changes during volleyball training session (Fig. 2). In the group of untrained players (Fig. 3A) the HGQ in control ranged 19,9 – 21,7 with mean $20,7 \pm 0,20$. After 30 min of exercise the HGQ ranged 22,6 – 23,2 with mean $20,9 \pm 0,18$. At the end of training, after 60 min of exercise, the HGQ ranged 24,3 – 25,7 with mean $24,8 \pm 0,30$. In the group of trained tennis players the HGQ changed during play in almost the same manner (see Fig. 3B). In control (before play) HGQ was $20,63 \pm 0,24$ (from 20,3 to 20,9); after 30 min of play it became $22,14 \pm 0,22$ (21,7 – 22,3); and after 60 min of play – $29,83 \pm 0,30$ (range from 24,4 to 25,7).

Discussion

It was demonstrated in this work that the sportive trainings (playing volleyball or tennis) induce the increase of HGQ and, therefore, chromatin condensation. There were some differences in reaction to sports exercise in groups of untrained

and trained volleyball players. After the first stage of training session (60 min) the increase of HGQ in untrained players was $9,2 \pm 1,2$ %, in relation to control, but in group of trained players it was lower – $5,6 \pm 2,6$ %. After the 120 min period of training session the differences in the relative HGQ increase between groups of untrained and trained players were insignificant – $19,4 \pm 2,3$ % and $23,5 \pm 2,9$ %, correspondently. No significant difference in relative HGQ increase between groups of untrained and trained tennis players during the training session was observed.

Typically, chromatin condensation phenomenon associated with the decreased activity of the biosynthetic processes in the cell nucleus [6]. Such reaction represents a nonspecific response to the action of damaging factors on a cellular level [8]. In the case of condensation of chromatin after sportive trainings the condensation of chromatin can be connected with the action of stress hormones that are produced in response to sport exercises. It was revealed that stress hormones hydrocortisone and epinephrine in concentrations close to the physiological ones induce an increase in HGQ [7,10]. Previously it was demonstrated that physical load (the cross-country run with loading during 8 – 10 h) induces the chromatin condensation [7]. The process of chromatin condensation in the course of sports training on a stationary training bicycle was also investigated. It was demonstrated that the degree of chromatin condensation increases in cells of all donors after first stage of sports training (400 W, 1 min) [11]. The results of the present study indicate the gradual increase of the degree of chromatin condensation in cells of all donors during playing sessions. As it was already mentioned, the physiological parameters in some cases not change during training sessions [4,5]. Namely in relation to tennis, the data analysis revealed no differences in balance performance among tennis players between pre and post tennis training session [12]. The data obtained in this work indicate the cell answer to the physical loadings applied to the organism of players in volleyball and tennis. So, notwithstanding the cells of buccal epithelium do not take part in the muscle work, they answer to changes in organism during sportive training sessions. The possible mechanism of it may be in the changes of hormones concentration during the training session.

Conclusion

Thus, the number of granules of heterochromatin in nuclei of cells of human buccal epithelium increases during training sessions in volleyball and tennis.

Assessment of heterochromatin granules quantity (HGQ assessment) in nuclei of buccal epithelium cells may be proposed as a new non-traumatic and painless method of determination of organism answer to sportive trainings. The HGQ assessment enables to detect individual differences in organism reaction to sportive trainings.

Conflict of Interests

Authors have no conflict of interests.

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